

HANDBOOK FOR ASTRONOMY CLUB PATRONS

PRAGSAC TEACHER TRAINING WORKSHOP

31st August – 2nd September 2022

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1. SCIENTIFIC THEORY AND THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD

The aim of this section is to give students a basic understanding of the scientific method, with a practical activity included to allow them to explore it for themselves.

Science is a systematic and logical approach to discovering how things in the universe work. It is also the body of knowledge accumulated through the discoveries about all the things in the universe.

Scientific method: A method of discovering knowledge about the natural world based on making falsifiable predictions (hypotheses), testing them empirically, and developing peer-reviewed theories that best explain the known data.

Hypothesis: A testable prediction that is arrived at logically from a theory.

THE BASIC STEPS OF THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD

The basic steps in the scientific method are:

- Observe a natural phenomenon and define a question about it.
- Make a hypothesis, or potential solution to the question.
- Test the hypothesis.
- If the hypothesis is true, find more evidence or find counter-evidence.
- If the hypothesis is false, create a new hypothesis or try again.
- Draw conclusions and repeat – the scientific method is never-ending, and no result is ever considered perfect.

EXAMPLE OF THE SCIENTIFIC METHOD

To better understand the process of the scientific method, take a look at the following example:

- Observation: My iron doesn't work.
- Question: Is something wrong with my electrical outlet?
- Hypothesis: If something is wrong with the outlet, my blender also won't work when plugged into it.
- Experiment: I plug my blender into the outlet.
- Result: My blender works!
- Conclusion: My electrical outlet works, but my iron still won't work.
- Refine the hypothesis: My iron is faulty.

A flowchart showing the Scientific Method. Credit: Lumenlearning

ACTIVITY – MYSTERY TUBE

This activity demonstrates the various processes involved in the scientific method, and also promotes teamwork, brainstorming, curiosity and creative thinking. (See Appendix 1).

Materials required:

T-roll tube (the inner cardboard tube without the T-roll tissue itself), string, scissors, (optionally glue and/or rubber bands, paper if you wish to cover the ends of the tube once completed).

Procedure:

1. Make a demonstration mystery tube, there are different ways it can be constructed, see Appendix 1. Ensure that the ends of the tube are covered with paper or fabric so that the strings inside the tube are not visible.
2. Show students the mystery tube, pull each of the strings so they can observe what happens
3. Ask students (in pairs or groups) to discuss/brainstorm and then draw how they think the strings are connected inside the tube
4. The students can then use the materials provided to make their own mystery tube to test their hypothesis of how the strings are connected.
5. Test their tubes by pulling the strings, do they behave in the same way as the demonstration tube? If so, that's great! If not, encourage the students to brainstorm again to refine their design.

Note: Do not reveal how the strings are actually connected in the demonstration tube! There is more than one way to make the tube so allow the students to come up with their own ideas.

USEFUL LINKS - SCIENTIFIC METHOD

Mystery tube activity - full details, including instructions for making a demonstration tube:

<http://lasp.colorado.edu/home/wp-content/uploads/2011/06/Mystery-Tube.pdf>

General information on scientific method:

<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-psychology/chapter/the-scientific-method/>

<https://www.livescience.com/20896-science-scientific-method.html>

2. EARTH/MOON/SUN SYSTEM

The aim of this section is to familiarise the students with the relationship between the Earth, Moon and Sun. Also the relative sizes of the 3 bodies, the distances between them, and how eclipses are formed.

EARTH

Using an Earth ball or a globe, ask some simple questions to make the students comfortable eg what is this? What are the blue parts? What are the green/brown parts? What are the white parts? What is at the top/bottom? Can you find Ghana?

Satellite image of the Earth. Credit: NASA

How does the Earth move? Students should be aware that the Earth:

- 1 – spins or rotates on its axis
- 2 – revolves or orbits around the Sun

To reinforce this in a fun way, you can get students to stand up and “be” the Earth, so they can demonstrate spinning on their axis. They can also get into pairs to show the Earth orbiting the Sun.

How long does it take for the Earth to rotate once on its axis? Approximately 24 hours. Why is this important for us? Because it gives us our night and day.

How long does it take for the Earth to orbit the Sun? Approximately 365 days. Why is this important for us? Because it gives us our year.

USEFUL LINKS - EARTH

General information on the Earth: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/planets/earth/overview/>

MOON

The moon is our nearest neighbour, and our only natural satellite.

How big is the moon compared to the Earth?

Using an Earth ball, globe or any large ball like a football to represent the Earth, ask students what size they think the moon would be **on the same scale**. You can use balls of different sizes, or cut out paper circles of different sizes and get the students to vote/put hands up for the one they think is the correct size of the moon on that scale.

Answer - The diameter of the moon is about $\frac{1}{4}$ the diameter of the Earth.

Diameter of Earth = 12,742km

Diameter of Moon = 3,474km

Comparison of Earth and Moon size. Credit: UK IOP (Institute of Physics)

How far is the moon from the Earth?

Get one student to hold the ball representing the Earth, another to hold the ball representing the moon. Ask the student holding the “moon” to stand where they think the moon would be **on that scale**. Other students can also stand at the position where they think the moon would be.

Answer - The correct distance is about 30 times the diameter of the ball representing the Earth!

The actual distance from the Earth to the moon is approximately 385,000km on average (the moon’s orbit is not exactly circular so sometimes the moon is closer to the Earth than at other times. Closest distance is 363,000km and furthest distance is 405,000km).

ACTIVITY – DEMONSTRATE THE EARTH-MOON DISTANCE

Option 1: Using the Earth and Moon balls as described above, wrap string around the Earth ball 10 times. When the string is unwound, its length represents the distance between the Earth and the Moon on that scale.

Option 2: The Earth – Moon Size Comparison page (see Appendix 2) has circles representing the Earth and Moon in the correct size proportions. Students draw and colour the Earth and Moon, cut them out and stick onto cardboard. Tape the end of a piece of string to one edge of the Earth circle, then wrap the string around the Earth circle 15 times. When the string is unwound, its length represents the distance between the Earth and the Moon on that scale. Tape the other end of the string to the Moon circle.

Phases of the Moon

Have you seen the moon at night? Does it always look the same? The different “shapes” of the moon (crescent, half, full etc.) are called PHASES. Have you noticed that it takes about a month for the moon to go through this cycle of phases before it starts repeating? The phases are due to the orbit of the moon around the Earth. It takes about a month for the moon to orbit the Earth and that’s why the cycle of phases also takes about a month.

*Phases of the moon
Credit: F.Espenak*

*Explanation and names of moon phases.
Credit: Andonee*

One way to remember that the moon takes a month to orbit the Earth is to refer to Ramadan; Ramadan lasts about a month, and the start and end of Ramadan are marked by the sighting of the new moon, hence it also takes a month to cycle through the phases of the moon, and therefore a month for the moon to orbit the Earth.

What does the moon look like?

When you look at the moon with the naked eye, you can see that there are dark and light areas on the surface. The light areas are the **highlands**, or mountains, the dark areas are called **Maria**, low-lying basins that became filled with lava. (The word “Maria” is the Latin word for “seas”, because early astronomers thought those areas might be water-filled oceans just like the ones on Earth).

Different cultures “see” different shapes in these dark/light areas. In Ghana, people say you can see a woman pounding fufu, other cultures see a rabbit, a face etc.

If you use binoculars or a telescope to view the moon you will see many circular features of different sizes on the surface, these are **craters**, and they mark where the moon was impacted by asteroids throughout its history. (The moon has no atmosphere and therefore no rain or wind to erode the craters away, that’s why they are still visible today).

Moon features. Credit: Sabrina Stanley

Moon craters. Credit: James Stuby (NASA)

ACTIVITY – WHAT I SEE IN THE MOON

Students are given a printout of the full moon (see Appendix 3), and can draw on it whatever shapes they think the dark and light areas make. They should write a short description of what they have drawn, or make up a story about it.

Earth-Moon System

Look at the 2 images below. Which one is our moon?

Credit: Wikipedia/NASA

Credit: Wikipedia/NASA

The left hand image is the most familiar, but both images are of our moon! The left hand image is the “near side” which is what we can see from Earth. The right hand image is the “far side” which we can only see from photographs taken by spacecraft. So as the moon orbits around the Earth, it keeps the same side facing the Earth all the time, this is known as “synchronous rotation”.

ACTIVITY – MOON ORBITING THE EARTH

Get the students into pairs, one is the Earth, the other is the moon, let them demonstrate how the moon orbits the Earth. The “moon” students usually rotate as they orbit. Explain that since we only ever see one side of the moon, the way the moon moves is different – the moon has to keep the same side facing the Earth all the time. This is called synchronous rotation and is quite common in the solar system.

Does the moon rotate?

We only ever see one side of the moon, so from our point of view on Earth, it seems that the Moon does not rotate. However, if you were looking at the Earth- moon system from space, then you would be able to see the moon slowly rotating as it orbits the Earth. So the moon does rotate, but the time it takes to rotate once on its axis is the same as the time it takes to orbit the Earth.

USEFUL LINKS - MOON

General information on the moon:

<https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/moons/earths-moon/overview/>

<https://moon.nasa.gov/about/in-depth/>

International Observe the Moon Night handbook, includes the activity above “What I See in the Moon”: <https://moon.nasa.gov/resources/367/international-observe-the-moon-night-guide/>

Images of the near and far sides of the moon:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Near_side_of_the_Moon

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Far_side_of_the_Moon

SUN

What type of object is our Sun? A star. What is a star? A ball of glowing gas.

Why is the Sun important to us on Earth? Its gravity keeps us in orbit. Almost all life uses energy from the Sun to live (apart from some life-forms in the deep ocean). The Sun powers our weather systems. However, the Sun can also be a danger since solar flares (intense bursts of radiation from a specific area on the surface of the Sun) can disrupt satellites and power grids.

An image of the sun (our star) with some details. Credit: NASA

How big is the Sun compared to the Earth?

ACTIVITY – SCALE MODEL OF THE SUN AND PLANETS

Materials required:

Manila card, scissors, sellotape, small skewers or toothpicks

1. Using manila card (you may have to tape 2 or 3 pieces together) cut out a circle of diameter 1m. This will represent the Sun.
2. Print out the Planets page (see Appendix 4) and cut out each of the planets. You can sellotape each one to a bamboo skewer or a toothpick to make a “handle”.
3. Let students compare the size of the Earth and other planets to the Sun.

The diameter of the Earth would fit approximately 109 times across the Sun, so the Sun is enormous compared to Earth! And even more enormous compared to the moon (since the moon is $\frac{1}{4}$ size of the Earth). Even the diameter of Jupiter, the largest planet, would fit about 10 times across the Sun.

What makes the Sun shine?

The Sun is composed of Hydrogen and Helium. At the core (centre) of the Sun, temperatures and pressures are so great that the Hydrogen is **fused** to form Helium plus energy. The energy makes its way from the core through to the surface where it is released as the light that we see and the heat that we feel.

ACTIVITY – MEASURE THE DIAMETER OF THE SUN

This activity allows students to measure the diameter of the Sun using the pinhole method.

1. Use a cardboard tube or make a tube out of rolled up paper or thin card.
2. Cover one end of the tube with baking paper/baking parchment, and the other end with foil.
3. Make a small hole in the foil with a pin.
4. Point the end of the tube with the hole towards the Sun
5. An image of the Sun should be formed on the baking paper at the other end.
6. Mark the size of the Sun on the paper with a pen, so it can be measured later

The diagram below shows the geometry of the arrangement, where d is the diameter of the image of the Sun formed on the paper, and l is the length of the tube.

Credit: NASE

Since the diagram shows 2 similar triangles, we can say:

$$\frac{D}{L} = \frac{d}{l}$$

Rearranging gives:

$$D = \frac{d * L}{l}$$

Given that L , the approximate distance from the Earth to the Sun = 150,000,000 km, students should be able to use their measurements to calculate D , the diameter of the Sun. See how close your students can get to the actual solar diameter of 1,392,000 km!

Note: This activity is from the Network for Astronomy School Education (NASE)

http://sac.csic.es/astrosecundaria/en/cursos/formato/materiales/conferencias/T3_en.pdf

ECLIPSES

What is an eclipse?

A **solar eclipse** happens when the moon passes between the Sun and the Earth, blocking out the Sun. But we know that the Earth is very small compared to the Sun, so the moon is even more tiny! So how can the tiny moon block out the enormous Sun? *Because the Sun is much further away!* The Sun is about 400 times bigger than the moon, but it is also about 400 times further away, and hence both the Sun and the moon appear to be the same size in the sky.

Geometry of a solar eclipse.
Credit: www.explorebigsky.com/

Geometry of a lunar eclipse
Credit: www.in-the-sky.org

A **lunar eclipse** happens when the Earth is between the Sun and the moon, so the Earth's shadow falls on the moon. The moon appears red during a lunar eclipse because the sunlight is filtered and refracted through the Earth's atmosphere.

*The Sun during a solar eclipse
Credit: Luc Viatour*

*The moon during a lunar eclipse
By Credit: Giuseppe Donatiello*

ACTIVITY – MODELLING SOLAR AND LUNAR ECLIPSES

Materials:

Large balls, small balls, torches

Procedure:

1. Get students into pairs or small groups
2. Give each group a large ball (to represent the Sun), a smaller ball (to represent the moon) and a torch.
3. Ask the students to arrange the 3 objects to show how a solar eclipse is formed.
Note: Make sure that the arrangement shows light from the torch falling onto the “Earth”, and then the smaller “moon” ball can be positioned so that its shadow falls onto the “Earth”.
4. Ask the students to rearrange the 3 objects to show how a lunar eclipse is formed
Note: This model will show the positions of the 3 objects during a lunar eclipse but it can't replicate the red colour of the moon.

Credit: Tomruen

Note: Sizes and distances not to scale!

A **solar eclipse** occurs in the daytime at **new moon**, when the Moon is between Earth and the Sun, while a **lunar eclipse** occurs at night at **full moon** when Earth passes between the Sun and the Moon

Summarising Solar and Lunar Eclipses:

- A solar eclipse happens during the day, and usually only lasts for a few minutes
- Only the people who live where the shadow of the moon falls on the Earth, will be able to see the eclipse

- There are usually 2 solar eclipses in a year, but occasionally there can be up to 5
- The next solar eclipse visible from Ghana will be 6 February 2027
- A lunar eclipse happens at night, and can last for up to 2 hours
- Anyone who can see the moon that night, can see the eclipse
- There are between 2 and 5 lunar eclipses in a year
- The next total lunar eclipse visible from Ghana will be 14 March 2025

Did you know that the Sun also rotates?

It was Galileo who first saw sunspots (dark spots that are cooler areas caused by magnetic activity) on the surface of the Sun and watched them move across the surface with time. He realized this meant that the Sun was rotating on its axis, as the Earth does. Because the Sun is made of gas, different parts of the Sun rotate at different speeds; the Sun rotates every 27 days at the equator, every 31 days at the poles.

*Galileo's sketch of sunspots.
Credit: galileo.rice.edu*

Sunspots on the Sun. Credit: NASA

USEFUL LINKS – SUN & ECLIPSES

General info on the Sun: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/solar-system/sun/overview/>

What makes the sun shine: <http://coolcosmos.ipac.caltech.edu/ask/2-How-does-the-Sun-shine->

Why does the moon look red during a lunar eclipse:

<https://www.timeanddate.com/eclipse/why-does-moon-look-red-lunar-eclipse.html>

All about eclipses: <https://www.mreclipse.com/>

General information about eclipses, includes a downloadable handbook and posters (written for the annular solar eclipse of June 2020, but much of the material is general):

<https://www.africanastronomicalsociety.org/solar-eclipse-2020/>

Measuring the diameter of the Sun activity:

http://sac.csic.es/astrosecundaria/en/cursos/formato/materiales/conferencias/T3_en.pdf

3. SOLAR SYSTEM

The aim of this section is for students to understand the components of the Solar System and the different regions within it. Also to gain an appreciation of the relative sizes of the various bodies and the distances between them.

COMPONENTS AND REGIONS OF THE SOLAR SYSTEM

Our Solar system comprises of the Sun, planets, dwarf planets, moons, asteroids and comets. The Solar system has different regions i.e. inner planets, asteroid belt, outer planets, Kuiper Belt.

Regions and components of the solar system. Credit: universetoday.com
Note – distances are not to scale!

Brief overview of the Components of the Solar System:

Sun	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The star at the centre of the Solar System • Generates huge amounts of energy in its core, this is why it “shines”. • Provides us with heat and light. • Its gravity keeps all the other solar system objects in orbit. • Contains over 99% of the mass in the entire solar system!
Planets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They orbit the Sun, are spherical, and have a clear orbital path. • The inner planets are “terrestrial” i.e. rocky, you can stand on the surface. • The outer planets are icy and gaseous i.e. no surface to stand on. • The 8 planets have different diameters, densities and number of moons
Dwarf planets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They orbit the Sun, are spherical, but do not have a clear orbital path. • Pluto is the most famous one but there are others.
Moons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moons are bodies which orbit a planet. • Some planets have no moons (Mercury and Venus), others have more than 70! (Jupiter and Saturn) • There are more than 150 moons in total in the solar system. • The moons are very different in terms of size, density and other properties.
Asteroids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asteroids are small bodies made of rock/dust/ice that are orbiting the Sun • Mainly found in the Asteroid Belt between Mars and Jupiter, although there are others elsewhere in the solar system. • Small asteroids enter the Earth’s atmosphere every day – most burn up forming a meteor (<i>shooting star</i>). • Bigger ones sometimes don’t burn up completely and land on the surface of the Earth (a <i>meteorite</i>.) • There is a danger that a very large asteroid could hit the Earth causing devastation – like the one that wiped out the dinosaurs – hence NASA and other agencies are working on detecting and monitoring asteroids.

Comets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small icy bodies from the outer reaches of the Solar System. • Have very elongated elliptical orbits – very different from the planetary orbits which are almost circular. • As they come nearer to the sun, the heat evaporates the ice forming the characteristic long tail. • Some well-known comets have well established regular orbits e.g. Halley’s Comet orbits the Sun every 76 years.
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Planets

Ask students if they can give the names of any of the planets. Then ask them to list the planets in the correct order from the Sun. (Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, Neptune).

Note: Some students may include Pluto as a planet, you can explain that it has now been reclassified as a dwarf planet. To be classified as a planet, a body must:

- 1 – orbit the Sun
- 2 – be approximately spherical
- 3 – have cleared its orbital path

Pluto fails on the third criteria and hence it is now classified as a dwarf planet.

Ask students what they know about the planets, differences or similarities between them. How is Earth different to all the other planets? (It’s the only planet that we know of that supports life).

A few key facts about the planets:

Mercury	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smallest planet and closest to the Sun • No moon
Venus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hottest planet even though it is not the closest to the Sun; thick clouds keep in the heat • Brightest planet in the night sky, often seen in the early evening or around dawn, so sometimes called the “<i>Evening Star</i>” or “<i>Morning Star</i>”. • No moon
Earth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our planet and only one that we know that supports life. • Water covers approx. 70% of the surface. • 1 moon.
Mars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Known as the red planet; it looks red because of the iron oxide in the rocks/dust on its surface. • Has the largest volcano in the Solar System – Olympus Mons. • Currently there are robotic rovers exploring its surface. • 2 small moons.
Jupiter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Largest planet. • Called a gas giant. • Well-known feature is the Great Red Spot, a huge storm that has been observed for 300 years, and is larger than the Earth! • Has a faint ring system! • Has 79 moons (as at January 2022)
Saturn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Known for its spectacular rings that consist of millions of small icy/rocky particles that are all orbiting the planet. • Called a gas giant. • Has 82 moons (as at January 2022).

Uranus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Called an ice giant. • Has a faint ring system. • Is tipped on its side! • Has 27 moons.
Neptune	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Called an ice giant. • Has a faint ring system. • Used to have a “Big Black Spot” – a storm like the one on Jupiter. • Has 13 moons.

*The inner or terrestrial planets in correct size proportion relative to one another
From left Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars Credit: Lunar and Planetary Institute*

*The outer or jovian planets in correct size proportion relative to one another
From left Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune Credit: Britannica.com*

ACTIVITY – PLANET RIDDLES WORKSHEET

This worksheet helps students revise their knowledge of the Solar System planets in a fun way. (See Appendix 5.)

ACTIVITY – COMPARISON OF PLANET SIZES

1. Give out a list of the planet sizes (diameters), or write them on a board. (See Appendix 6.)
2. Students get into groups and use different materials to model the planets, showing them in the correct sizes relative to each other. Here are 3 different possible options:
 - Cut out circles of paper to represent the planets. Older students can use ratios to create accurate scale models. Younger students can estimate.
 - Use balls of different sizes, or balloons inflated to different sizes to represent the planets

- Use household objects of different sizes such as bowls, plates, tins etc to represent the planets
3. Let the students go round the room looking at the models made by other groups. Have they learned anything surprising about the planet sizes? Which models are the most accurate? Most effective?

Note: the main point of this activity is for the students to get a general feel for the relative sizes of the planets eg they should appreciate that Venus is only slightly smaller than Earth, that Mars is about half the size of Earth, that Jupiter’s diameter is more than 10 times the diameter of Earth etc. This is more important than the absolute numerical accuracy of the models.

Distances between the planets

Pictures of the solar system in text books don’t show the correct scale, it is often surprising to see the true distances between the planets.

ACTIVITY - SCALE MODEL OF THE SOLAR SYSTEM USING TOILET PAPER

1. Get students into groups, give each group a list of planet distances from the Sun, or write it on the board. (See Appendix 6). Give each group a toilet roll.
2. Using the list of planet distances, groups have to decide on the scale they will use for their model eg 1 square of toilet paper = xx km
3. Using the toilet paper and the scale they have decided on, students create a model of the distances from the Sun to each of the planets
4. Note: They can either mark all the planet distances on one long piece of toilet paper, or have separate pieces of toilet paper for the distance from each planet to the Sun

ADDITIONAL ACTIVITY – SORTING THE SOLAR SYSTEM

Try out this card game where students try their hand at classifying objects in the Solar System:

<http://www.dunlap.utoronto.ca/~du/Webinars/Activity-SortingSolarSystem.pdf>

Planet Day and Year

An interesting idea is the concept of a “day” and a “year” for the planets. Challenge the students to explain what this means. And so, can they explain how a day on Venus is longer than a year on Venus?

What we call a “day” is the time it takes the Earth to rotate once on its axis. So each planet also has its own “day” – the time it takes to rotate on its axis.

What we call a “year” is the time it takes the Earth to orbit the Sun. Each planet also has its own “year” – the time that planet takes to orbit the Sun.

Here are the “days” and “years” for each of the solar system planets:

Planet	Rotation period (day)	Orbital period (year)
Mercury	1,408 hours (59 days)	88 days
Venus	5,832 hours (243 days)	225 days
Earth	24 hours (1 day)	365 days (1 year)
Mars	25 hours	687 days
Jupiter	10 hours	12 years
Saturn	11 hours	30 years
Uranus	17 hours	84 years
Neptune	16 hours	165 years

USEFUL LINKS – SOLAR SYSTEM

General info on the Solar System: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/solar-system/our-solar-system/overview/>

Planets of the Solar System: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/planets/overview/>

Moons of the Solar System: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/moons/overview/>

Asteroids and other small Solar System bodies: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/small-bodies/overview/>

These 2 websites compare the characteristics of the various planets:

<https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/planet-compare/>

<https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/>

Information from IAU on reclassification of Pluto: <https://www.iau.org/public/themes/pluto/>

Planet riddles worksheet: https://www.superteacherworksheets.com/space/planet-riddles_WMTZD.pdf

4. OUR GALAXY, THE MILKY WAY

The aim of this section is to provide students with a basic understanding of the size, structure and composition of our galaxy, the Milky Way, and the position of our Solar System within it.

WHAT IS A GALAXY?

A galaxy is a collection of stars, gas and dust, held together by gravity. The size and shape of galaxies vary, as can the number of stars within it. Typical galaxies contain 100-200 billion stars, but some only contain a few million and others can contain trillions! All the stars orbit the centre of the galaxy, where there is usually a supermassive black hole.

THE MILKY WAY GALAXY

Our solar system is situated in a galaxy that we call the **Milky Way galaxy**. Our Sun is just one of about 100 - 200 billion stars in the Milky Way. Our galaxy is shaped like a spiral and is around 100,000 light years across (a light year is the distance that light travels in one year and is approximately 9.5 trillion km or 9.5×10^{12} km)

Credit: NASA/JPL-Caltech (left) / ESA ATG medialab (right)

The image above shows what we believe our galaxy looks like, face-on and edge-on. The image is an illustration not a real photo because we cannot get far enough outside the galaxy to be able to take such a photo. Astronomers worked out the shape of our galaxy using observations of the positions of stars in our galaxy and observations of other galaxies. Our Sun is not at the centre of our galaxy but is positioned about 2/3 of the way out from the centre, along one of the spiral arms.

On a clear night, if you are away from city lights, you may be able to see part of the Milky Way, which will look like a cloudy band of light across the sky. It is believed that the ancient Greeks gave the Milky Way its name, because it looked like a river or path of milk.

View of the Milky Way above the VLT in Paranal, Chile. Credit: ESO/Y. Beletsky

ACTIVITY – GALAXYSCAPE

Challenge the students to make a model of the Milky Way, that clearly shows what they have learned about the structure such as the bar shaped bulge in the centre, the spiral arms and the position of the Sun.

They can use any of the following methods:

- Use materials found in the natural world around them eg twigs, leaves, stones etc
- Use recycled materials found at school or at home eg plastic bottle caps, straws etc
- Use their own bodies!

The students can work in groups and can examine the other groups work when they are finished.

(This activity is used by permission of Discover the Universe <https://www.discovertheuniverse.ca/>)

USEFUL LINKS – MILKY WAY

NASA Solar System Exploration, Beyond our Solar System: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/solar-system/beyond/in-depth/>

What is the Milky Way Galaxy: <https://earthsky.org/astronomy-essentials/what-is-the-milky-way-galaxy/>

Milky Way galaxy: Facts about our cosmic neighborhood: <https://www.space.com/19915-milky-way-galaxy.html>

Meerkat radio image of the heart of the Milky Way - 2022: <https://www.sarao.ac.za/media-releases/new-meerkat-radio-image-reveals-complex-heart-of-the-milky-way/>

Article about the first Image of the Black hole at the Centre of the Milky Way: <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-61412463>

5. GALAXIES & OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

The aim of this section is to provide students with a basic understanding of what galaxies are and their main characteristics. Also to give an appreciation of the place of our planet in the wider universe.

GALAXY CLASSIFICATION

We already know that a galaxy is a collection of stars, gas and dust, held together by gravity. Galaxies can be different in terms of shape, size, numbers of stars, age etc. The basic classification of galaxies is by shape – elliptical, spiral, barred spiral or irregular, as shown below.

*Giant elliptical galaxy, M87.
Credit: ESA/Hubble & NASA*

*Spiral galaxy NGC 3344
Credit: ESA/Hubble & NASA*

*Barred spiral galaxy NGC 1073
Credit: NASA/ESA*

*Irregular galaxy NGC 4214
Credit: NASA/STScI*

Edwin Hubble was an American astronomer who studied galaxies and in 1926 came up with a method for classifying galaxies according to their shape, often known as the Hubble “tuning fork” diagram:

Hubble “Tuning Fork” Diagram

E = Elliptical
The numbers indicate how elliptical the galaxy is

S = Spiral
SB = Barred Spiral
The letters indicate whether the spiral arms are tightly wound or further apart

Credit: Ohio State University

Galaxies can interact, collide and merge. The Andromeda Galaxy is a spiral galaxy which is the closest large galaxy to the Milky Way. Observations show that Andromeda is moving towards the Milky Way and scientists believe they will eventually collide and possibly merge (but don't worry, this won't happen for another 5 billion years or so!)

The Antenna galaxies (NGC 4038 and NGC 4039), are currently undergoing a galactic collision, as can be seen by the long tails of stars, gas and dust.

Credit: ESA/Hubble

Galaxies are not equally spaced throughout the universe but are found in groups of about 20 – 50 galaxies, and these groups are themselves located within larger clusters and superclusters.

ACTIVITY – GALAXY SORTING/CLASSIFICATION

This activity has 4 phases, and should take place after the students have gained some general information about galaxies but have NOT been introduced to galaxy classification or the Hubble scheme. The aim of the activity is for students to work like scientists to classify images of galaxies using a classification scheme of their own devising.

- 1- Students work in groups, each group is given images of galaxies (see Appendix 8) and is challenged to come up with their own classification system.
- 2 – Each group presents its scheme to the rest of the class for discussion
- 3 - Students are introduced to the Hubble classification scheme and then classify the galaxies again, this time using the Hubble scheme
- 4 – Students discuss their results; were there differences between their scheme and Hubble's? Which one do they think is “better”? Were all the galaxies easy to classify?

This activity, *Galaxy Sorting*, is from the *Astronomical Society of the Pacific*:
https://astrosociety.org/file_download/inline/3e7de3ff-cbbd-4a8c-aae1-36f4d6a927fa

OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

For us, Earth is the most important planet in the universe because it is our home, however it is useful to understand Earth's place within the wider universe.

- We live on planet **Earth**, which is the only known planet in the universe that supports life. It is about 4.6 billion years old. The earliest life forms emerged more than 3 billion years ago.
- The Earth is part of the **Solar System** which comprises of eight planets, plus dwarf planets, moons, comets and asteroids with the Sun at its centre.
- The Solar System is found in the **Milky Way galaxy**. Our Sun is just one of 100-200 billion stars in the Milky Way.
- The Milky Way is located in the **Local Group** which contains more than 30 galaxies, and covers a distance of around 10 million light years
- The Local Group is part of the **Virgo Supercluster** which contains over 100 galaxies
- There are believed to be over 100 billion galaxies, in groups and clusters, in the known universe.

Earth's place in the Universe. Credit: Wikimedia

ACTIVITY – OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

Fill in the blanks revision worksheet (see Appendix 9).

ACTIVITY – COSMIC SURVEY

Students are provided with seven images of objects from our universe. Their task is to sort the images into order by size, distance or age (see Appendix 10).

USEFUL LINKS – GALAXIES AND OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

Galaxies: <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/space/universe/galaxies/>

The Hubble classification scheme for Galaxies: <https://esahubble.org/images/heic9902o/>

Beyond the Solar System: <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/solar-system/beyond/in-depth/>

Local Group: https://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/features/cosmic/local_group_info.html

Our place in the universe: <https://earthlyuniverse.com/universe-brief-tour-cosmic-address/>

6. THE ELECTROMAGNETIC (EM) SPECTRUM

The aim of this section is to give students an appreciation of the electromagnetic (EM) spectrum and its importance to astronomy.

The EM spectrum is a range or family of Radiations. What we call light is “visible light”, just one type of EM radiation, but there are many other types. Students may have heard of some of the other types of radiation: Ultraviolet (UV), Infrared (IR), Radio, Microwave, X-rays and gamma rays. These various types of radiation differ from each other in terms of wavelength, with radio waves having the longest wavelength and gamma rays the shortest.

The Electromagnetic Spectrum. Source: Researchgate.net

The EM spectrum is important to astronomy because objects in the universe emit not only visible light, but all the other types of EM radiation. Some types of objects emit more of one type of radiation than another. We can find out more about these objects by examining all the different types of light they emit.

For example:

- Dust between stars emits IR radiation
- Stars, certain types of galaxies and pulsars (rapidly spinning neutron stars) emit radio waves
- Hot gas around black holes emits X-rays

Our eyes are sensitive to a specific range of wavelengths and hence can only detect visible light but we can build different types of telescopes or detectors that can see/detect the other types of EM radiation. GRAO (Ghana Radio Astronomy Observatory) at Kuntunse is a radio telescope ie it detects radio waves.

Ghana Radio Astronomy Observatory (GRAO), at Kuntunse, Accra. Credit: GRAO

ACTIVITY – INVISIBLE PARTS OF THE EM SPECTRUM

To show that there are other types of radiation invisible to our eyes, You will need a remote control (e.g. for AC, TV etc.). When you press any button on the remote, an IR (infra red) beam is emitted, although our eyes cannot detect this. However, if you look through a digital camera or phone camera while pressing the button on the remote, a light is visible! So the phone camera can detect the IR beam that our eyes cannot.

USEFUL LINKS – EM SPECTRUM

Basic introduction for kids:

<https://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/science/toolbox/emspectrum1.html>

NASA Science series exploring the EM spectrum, there are links to the other sections of the series, which all include videos: https://science.nasa.gov/ems/01_intro -

Booklet developed by UNawe (Universe Awareness) which gives explanations and lots of activities to help children/students understand the “invisible universe”:

http://www.unawe.org/static/archives/education/pdf/Radioastronomy_activity_booklet.pdf

7. TELESCOPES

The aim of this section is to provide students with a basic understanding about astronomical telescopes and an appreciation of the different types of telescopes.

What is a telescope? A telescope is a tool that we can use to look at objects in the sky.

Why do we use a telescope? It makes things that are very far away appear closer so that we can study the objects in detail

Who uses a telescope? Astronomers use telescopes as a tool to see faraway objects that our eyes cannot see details of. eg stars, planets, moons, galaxies etc.

When was the telescope invented? The telescope has been around for over 400 years, and is believed to have been invented around 1608. The Italian astronomer Galileo Galilei did not invent the telescope but was one of the first people to design one that was good enough to observe stars, planets and moons, and he was among the first to make such observations. He built a very simple telescope using a wooden tube and two lenses.

Types of Telescopes

The first telescopes used lenses to gather the light from distant objects and make them appear larger and brighter. They are known as **refracting telescopes**, or **refractors**.

Credit: Las Cumbres Observatory Spacebook

The larger the lens, the more light the telescope can gather. The longer the focal length, the larger the image produced.

The largest refracting telescope in the world is at the Yerkes observatory in Wisconsin, USA, which has an objective lens 40 inches (1.02m) in diameter.

Isaac Newton invented a telescope that used mirrors instead of lenses in 1668. They are known as **reflecting telescopes**, or **reflectors**.

Credit: sciencefacts.net

Different types of reflectors use different types and combinations of mirrors:

Credit: sciencefacts.net

The largest single mirrors are typically around 8m – 9m in diameter. However the largest reflectors have segmented mirrors, for example the Southern African Large Telescope (SALT) has a mirror made up of 91 hexagonal segments, giving a diameter of 11m. SALT is the largest telescope in the southern hemisphere.

Multiwavelength Astronomy

The first telescopes detected only visible light. Nowadays, different types of telescopes can be designed to detect light from different regions of the Electromagnetic Spectrum:

1. Optical telescope detects or collects visible light
2. Infrared telescope detects or collects infrared light
3. Radio telescope detects or collects radio waves
4. Ultraviolet telescope detects or collects Ultraviolet light
5. X-ray telescopes detects or collects X-rays
6. Gamma ray telescope detects or collects gamma rays

Did you know that Ghana has a radio telescope? The Ghana Radio Astronomy Observatory (GRAO) houses a radio telescope with a 32m dish.

Telescopes in Space

There are two main reasons for operating a telescope from space, rather than from the ground:

- 1 – telescopes on the ground can be affected by the distortions of our atmosphere
- 2 – some parts of the electromagnetic spectrum are blocked by our atmosphere and hence cannot be detected from the ground. Only visible light and radio waves (plus a little Infra-red and Ultra-violet) can be detected from the ground.

Credit: STSci/JHU/NASA

The James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) is the latest and largest telescope to be launched into space, in December 2021. JWST detects Infra-red light and is already sending back spectacular images of our universe.

Telescope Arrays

A telescope array is a group of telescopes that can be made to work together as if they were a single, much bigger telescope. The Square Kilometre Array (SKA) will be the largest telescope in

the world when it is completed, and will consist of thousands of individual antennas in South African and Australia.

USEFUL LINKS - TELESCOPES

How do telescopes work? <https://museumsvictoria.com.au/scienceworks/visiting/melbourne-planetarium/fact-sheets/how-do-telescopes-work/>

Galileo and the Telescope: <https://www.loc.gov/collections/finding-our-place-in-the-cosmos-with-carl-sagan/articles-and-essays/modeling-the-cosmos/galileo-and-the-telescope>

Multiwavelength Astronomy: <https://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/science/toolbox/multiwavelength1.html>

ESA's Fleet across the Spectrum: <https://sci.esa.int/web/education/-/59465-esa-fleet-across-the-spectrum-poster>

James Webb Space Telescope: <https://webbtelescope.org/>

Square Kilometre Array (SKA): <https://www.skatelescope.org/the-ska-project/>

8. SATELLITES

WHAT IS A SATELLITE?

A **satellite** is an object in space that orbits around a bigger object.

There are **two (2)** kinds/categorization of satellites: **natural** (such as the moon orbiting the Earth) and **artificial** (such as the International Space Station orbiting the Earth).

A **Natural satellite** is any celestial body in space that orbits around a larger body.

Artificial satellites are satellites made by people and launched into orbit using rockets.

Satellite communication consists of **three (3)** main components

- Uplink
- Satellite transponder
- Downlink

Uplink: An uplink earth station transmits the desired signal to the satellite.

Transponder: The satellite transponder amplifies the incoming signal and changes the frequency.

Downlink: The satellite transponder transmits the signal to downlink earth station and the ground equipment receives the signal.

TYPES OF SATELLITE ORBITS

On the basis of Inclination - we have three (3) types of satellite orbits

- Equatorial orbit
- Inclined orbit
- Polar orbit

Equatorial orbit: An equatorial orbit is when the satellite rotates in an orbit directly above the equator, usually in a circular path. It has an inclination of 0 degree.

Inclined orbit:

Inclined orbits are virtually all orbits except those that travel directly above the equator or directly above the North and South Poles. The angle of inclination varies between 0 to 180 degrees.

Polar orbit:

A polar orbit is when the satellite rotates in a path that takes it over the North and South Poles in an orbital pattern that is perpendicular to the equatorial plane. Polar orbiting satellites follow a low altitude path close to earth's surface, passing over and very close to both the North and South Poles. The angle of inclination of a satellite in a polar orbit is nearly 90 degrees.

On the basis of altitude from Earth - the types of orbits are classified into:

- Low Earth orbit (LEO)
- Medium earth orbit (MEO)
- Geostationary earth orbit (GEO)

Low Earth orbit (LEO):

Low earth orbit satellites operate at a distance of about 160 to 2,000 kilometres above the earth's surface. They take approximately 90 to 120 minutes to circle the Earth.

Medium earth orbit (MEO):

Medium earth orbit is the region of space around the Earth above low Earth orbit and below geostationary orbit. The orbital periods of Medium earth orbit satellites range from about two to six hours. This satellite operates at altitudes between 2,000 kilometers and 35,786 kilometers above the earth's surface.

Geostationary earth orbit (GEO):

A geostationary satellite is an earth-orbiting satellite which is placed at an altitude of approximately 35,786 kilometers directly over the equator. It revolves in the same direction the earth rotates that means west to east. This satellite takes 24 hours to orbit the Earth.

On the basis of the shape - orbits are also classified into two types:

- Circular orbit
- Elliptical orbit

Circular orbit:

Circular orbit is the orbit with a fixed distance around the barycenter, that is, in the shape of a circle. This orbit has an eccentricity of 0.

There are several types of circular orbits, and they include:

- Geostationary Orbit
- Polar Orbit
- Equatorial orbit

Elliptical Orbit:

An elliptical orbit is the revolving of one object around another in an oval-shaped path called an ellipse.

The eccentricity of an elliptical orbit is greater than 0 but less than 1.

Sometimes these satellites are closer, and at other times they are farther away from earth.

The closest point a satellite comes to Earth is called its **perigee**.

The farthest point is the **apogee**.

The most common example of elliptical orbit is highly elliptical orbit.

TYPES OF ARTIFICIAL SATELLITES

Navigation satellite:

- A satellite navigation system used to determine the ground position of an object.
- It determines the geographic location of ships, aircrafts, or any other object.
- It is also vital to military forces.
- It is often used for gathering intelligence used for military purposes or as a military weapon.

Weather satellite:

Weather satellites are primarily used for the following

- to monitor the weather and climate of the Earth.
- to predict daily weather conditions, such as temperature and rainfall.
- to monitor how weather conditions, like storms, hurricanes, cyclone, tropical storms, develop and change over time.

Communications satellite:

The communication satellite is a satellite that transmits the signals such as telephone, television, radio, internet signals over long distances.

ACTIVITY – ANALYSING SATELLITE DATA

Divide students into 4 groups, each group will examine a different aspect of the satellite images provided by the facilitator. Students can discuss what the images are showing and how the information could be useful to different parts of the community or to policymakers.

USEFUL LINKS - SATELLITES

What is a satellite?: <https://www.space.com/24839-satellites.html>

Types of orbits: https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Space_Transportation/Types_of_orbits

10 ways that satellites helped you today: <https://www.asc-csa.gc.ca/eng/satellites/everyday-lives/10-ways-that-satellites-helped.asp>

NASA's Earth Science Missions – Current Fleet: <https://science.nasa.gov/earth-science/earth-missions-current>

9. USEFUL ASTRONOMY RESOURCES

Discover the Universe – free online astronomy training courses for teachers

www.discovertheuniverse.ca/

Online astronomy textbook

<https://www.teachastronomy.com/>

List of astronomy education and outreach resources from the OAD (Office for Astronomy Development)

<https://www.astro4dev.org/resources/education-outreach/>

Website and online textbook for teaching Astronomy / Earth Science / Climate Change

<https://grade8science.com/ngss/>

A career among the stars (from SAAO – South African Astronomical Observatory)

<https://www.sao.ac.za/opportunities/careers/>

APPENDICES – ACTIVITY PRINTOUTS

APPENDIX 1: MYSTERY TUBE

There are different ways that the mystery tube can be constructed, here are some ideas:

Credit: lasp.colorado.edu

Ignore the measurement shown, this can be made from a smaller tube such as the inner tube of T-roll or kitchen roll

Credit: Understanding Science, University of Berkeley

As above this can be made from a cardboard tube instead of a PVC pipe, but note the use of a ring connecting the strings inside the tube

APPENDIX 2: EARTH – MOON SIZE COMPARISON

If the Earth was a sphere the size of the circle above...

Then the Moon would be a sphere the size of the circle below...

APPENDIX 3: WHAT I SEE IN THE MOON

What I See in the Moon

A long time ago...

Source: <https://moon.nasa.gov/resources/367/international-observe-the-moon-night-guide/>

APPENDIX 4: PLANET PRINTOUTS

Source: <http://www.iop.org/activity/outreach/resources/pips/topics/earth/index.html>

APPENDIX 5: PLANET RIDDLES

Name: _____

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Planet Riddles

1. I'm the planet that everyone calls "Red,"
But really my soil is rust-colored instead.
Look up and you may spot me in the sky,
I'm the orange-colored dot, way up high.

Which planet am I? _____

2. With over 63 moons, you might say I have a lot.
Look with a telescope to see my big, red spot.
The spot is a wind storm, swirling around.
High in the night sky is where I can be found.

Which planet am I? _____

3. I'm blue and green and a little brown.
I'm a small planet with life all around.
They call me the third rock from the sun.
I don't have many moons - just one.

Which planet am I? _____

4. No matter how hard you look, you'll never find me,
Unless you have a telescope to help you see.
I was once called a planet, but not any more.
Now I'm just a "Dwarf Planet," but too important to ignore.

Which planet am I? _____

5. Look very close to the sun and you'll spot,
A tiny, cratered planet that's very hot.
I have no moons but I orbit the sun very fast.
Can you guess my name at last?

Which planet am I? _____

Planet Riddles

6. I'm yellow and cloudy and super hot.
Look low in the sky, I'm easy to spot.
People call me the "Evening Star"
From planet Earth, I'm not very far.

Which planet am I? _____

7. Named for the Roman god of the Sea,
Look past Saturn and Uranus for me.
I had a black spot that was a huge storm.
Now it's all gone, but I'll still never be warm.

Which planet am I? _____

8. I'm a giant gas planet out in space,
There are bands or stripes all over my face.
When it comes to size, I'm number two,
I have bright rings. That's an easy clue.

Which planet am I? _____

9. A gas planet that's off in the distance,
Only recently they found my rings in existence.
I'm blue and cold and far away,
People say I'm funny because I spin sideways.

Which planet am I? _____

PLANET RIDDLES - ANSWER KEY

Riddle 1 – Mars

Riddle 2 – Jupiter

Riddle 3 – Earth

Riddle 4 – Pluto

Riddle 5 – Mercury

Riddle 6 – Venus

Riddle 7 – Neptune

Riddle 8 – Saturn

Riddle 9 - Uranus

APPENDIX 6: PLANET SIZES

Object	Diameter (km)	Compared to Earth
Mercury	4,880	38%
Venus	12,104	95%
Earth	12,742	100%
Mars	6780	53%
Jupiter	139,820	1,120%
Saturn	116,460	945%
Uranus	50,724	400%
Neptune	49,244	388%
Pluto	2,377	18%
Earth's Moon	3,474	27%

APPENDIX 7: PLANET DISTANCES

Planet	Distance from the Sun (Million km)
MERCURY	57
VENUS	108
EARTH	150
MARS	228
ASTEROID BELT	329 to 479
JUPITER	779
SATURN	1430
URANUS	2880
NEPTUNE	4550
PLUTO/KUIPER BELT	5900

APPENDIX 8 – GALAXY SORTING

M32

M101

M65

M109

M82

M51

Large Magellanic Cloud

Arp 252

NGC 4565

M81

M87

M104

NGC 2146

NGC 1365

NGC 4650a

NGC 6946

Leo 1

NGC 253

M59

NGC 1073

Source: Galaxy Sorting activity from the Astronomical Society of the Pacific:
https://astrosociety.org/file_download/inline/3e7de3ff-cbbd-4a8c-aae1-36f4d6a927fa

APPENDIX 9: OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

UNDERSTANDING OUR PLACE IN THE UNIVERSE

Fill in the blanks using the keywords below:

The Sun is a _____ located at the centre of our _____.

Our home, called _____, is one of 8 planets that orbit around the _____.

Earth has one _____ that orbits around it each month, showing different phases. Some planets have many moons that _____ around them. _____ is the largest planet in the Solar System and has over 70 moons! Our Sun is one of about _____ stars contained in the _____ we call the Milky Way. Astronomers are now discovering other _____ that orbit around some of those distant stars. Outer space is even bigger yet because the Milky Way is only one of an estimated 100 billion (100,000,000,000) galaxies in the _____!

Source: Adapted from Space Science Institute's Alien Earths program www.alienearths.org

APPENDIX 10: COSMIC SURVEY

Saturn

Pleiades Star Cluster

Hubble Space Telescope

Sun

Whirlpool Galaxy

Hubble Deep Field Galaxies

Moon

Source: Cosmic Questions Educators Guide:
<https://web.cfa.harvard.edu/seuforum/download/CQEdGuide.pdf>